

Antimony(V) tungstate as a new inorganic ion exchanger useful for removal of chromium(VI), mercury(II) and lead(II)

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A new inorganic ion exchanger antimony(V) tungstate (AT) has been synthesized under varying conditions. Distribution coefficients (K_d) of 16 transition metal ions have been studied in DMW, 0.1 M HCl, 0.1 M HCl + 10% DMSO (1 : 10) and 1 M NH_4Cl systems, and some analytically important separations of metal ions have been investigated. The greater selectivity behavior of the exchanger for Cr^{VI} , Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} has been utilized for the removal and recovery of these metal ions from dilute water samples.

Inorganic ion exchangers have been found more successful than the adsorbents for the removal and recovery of toxic metal ions from dilute aqueous solutions due to their specific selectivity¹. Antimonates of Zr^{IV} , Ti^{IV} , Fe^{III} and Sn^{IV} , tungstates of Sn^{IV} , Ti^{IV} , Fe^{III} and Bi^{III} have already been studied as inorganic ion exchangers. These materials are generally temperature resistant and stable under chemical attack. This note reports the synthesis and ion exchange behavior towards transition metal ions and analytical applications of antimony(V) tungstate as a new two-component inorganic ion exchanger.

Results and discussion

The results of ion exchanger capacity studies by various samples of antimony(V) tungstate reveal that AT_1 prepared by mixing 0.1 mol dm^{-3} solutions of antimony(V) chloride and sodium tungstate has maximum ion exchange capacity, 1.0 meq (dry g)⁻¹. Hence sample AT_1 was chosen for further studies. The ion exchanger capacity data determined for various cations (Table 1) show that the values for alkali metals is higher than the alkaline earths.

The chemical stability of the exchanger AT_1 was studied in different solvents, viz. HNO_3 (1 and 4 mol dm^{-3}), HCl

(1 and 2 mol dm^{-3}), NaOH (0.1 mol dm^{-3}), NH_4OH (0.1 mol dm^{-3}) and NH_4NO_3 (1 mol dm^{-3}). The results indicate that the material is fairly stable in water, and in 1 mol dm^{-3} NH_4NO_3 , HCl and HNO_3 . The effect of drying temperature of ion exchange capacity revealed that the exchanger can be used upto 100° without loss in ion-exchange capacity.

The results of pH-titration indicate that the exchanger AT_1 in H^+ -form behaves as a monoprotic weak acid. The total ion exchange capacity is 2.1 meq/g calculated at the neutralization point. This gives the maximum number of replaceable counter ions and is independent of nature of cation.

Chemical analysis of AT_1 were found as follows : Sb, 22.7; W, 42.7% (Calcd. for : Sb, 22.5; W, 42.4%). It revealed IR data at 3640–3120 (interstitial water molecules and OH), 1500 (def. of interstitial molecules), 740, 690, 650, 610, 570, 530, 500, 440 and 410 (polymerization through M–O linkage) and 1330 cm^{-1} (antimonic acid)². Based on the above results the following tentative formula has been assigned : $[(\text{Sb}_2\text{O}_5)(\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4)_{2.5}] \cdot 7.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

In order to study the selectivity behavior of the exchanger for transition metal ions, the distribution coefficients of 16 metal ions were measured in four different systems, and the results are summarized in Table 2. The ion exchanger material showed high selectivity (high K_d values) for Pb^{II} , Hg^{II} , Cr^{VI} , Ru^{VIII} , Al^{III} and Pt^{IV} .

The utility of the material was demonstrated by achieving the separations of metal ions (Table 3). Only small volume of eluents were required to give compact chromatograms and no tailing was observed during the elution of various metal ions. The recovery of the eluted metal ions is quantitative within experimental error range.

The results of comparative study of other inorganic ion exchangers (mainly tungstates of some multivalent metal salts) prepared so far with antimony(V) tungstate (Table 4)

Table 1. Ion exchange capacity for various cations

Cation	pH	Hydrated radius	Ion-exchange capacity, meq/g dry exchanger
Li^{I}	6.8	0.340	0.90
Na^{I}	6.7	0.276	1.00
K^{I}	6.8	0.232	1.25
Mg^{II}	6.5	0.700	0.70
Ca^{II}	6.5	0.630	0.92
Sr^{II}	6.4	–	0.98
Ba^{II}	6.1	0.590	1.00

Table 2. K_d values of metal ions on antimony(v) tungstate (AT₁) in different systems

Metal ion	K_d values, ml g ⁻¹			
	DMW	0.1 M HCl	0.1 M HCl +10% DMSO (1 : 10)	1 M NH ₄ Cl
Ni ^{II}	275	238	141	87
Pb ^{II}	875	170	407	63
Cu ^{II}	68	22	144	15
Hg ^{II}	411	367	300	250
Co ^{II}	268	98	49	24
Zn ^{II}	97	12	20	10
Mn ^{II}	121	26	95	14
Cd ^{II}	265	85	246	89
Pd ^{II}	300	36	100	36
Cr ^{VI}	870	556	800	570
Ru ^{VIII}	780	426	624	386
Pt ^{IV}	460	138	374	178
Zr ^{IV}	204	138	85	23
Fe ^{III}	71	33	26	10
Ca ^{II}	36	16	38	27
Mg ^{II}	19	8	28	15
Al ^{III}	670	205	640	140
Au ^{III}	28	1	16	2
Ba ^{II}	54	39	55	35
Sr ^{II}	40	31	45	30

Table 3. Quantitative separations of metal ions on antimony(v) tungstate (sample AT₁) column

Sl. no.	Metal ion	Eluent	Eluate ml	Amount loaded μ g	Amount found μ	Error %
1.	Zn ^{II}	0.5 M NH ₄ Cl	30	262	262	0.0
	Cd ^{II}	1 M NH ₄ Cl + 0.1 M HCl	40	337	339	+0.6
	Hg ^{II}	0.01 M EDTA + 0.1 M HCl	50	401	397	-1.0
2.	Fe ^{III}	0.5 M NH ₄ Cl	30	223	223	0.0
	Ni ^{II}	1 M NH ₄ Cl + 0.1 M HCl	50	225	222	-1.3
	Cr ^{VI}	0.1 M DPC + 0.1 M HCl	50	260	264	+1.5
3.	Cu ^{II}	0.1 M NH ₄ Cl	40	317	318	+0.3
	Co ^{II}	1 M NH ₄ Cl	40	245	243	-0.8
	Hg ^{II}	0.01 M EDTA + 0.1 M HCl	50	401	396	-1.3
4.	Au ^{III}	1 M Thiourea + 0.1 M HCl	30	197	197	0.0
	Cu ^{II}	0.1 M HCl	40	317	318	+0.3
	Al ^{III}	0.01 M EDTA + 0.1 M HCl	50	260	256	-1.5
5.	Fe ^{III}	1 M NH ₄ Cl	30	223	223	0.0
	Pt ^{IV}	5% KI + 0.1 M HCl	40	195	194	-0.5
	Ru ^{VIII}	0.1 M Thiourea + 0.1 M HCl	50	200	202	+1.0
6.	Mn ^{II}	0.1 M HCl	30	440	439	-0.2
	Ni ^{II}	1 M NH ₄ Cl + 0.1 M HCl	50	225	223	-0.9
7.	Zn ^{II}	0.5 M NH ₄ Cl	30	262	262	0.0
	Pb ^{II}	1 M NH ₄ Cl + 0.1 M HCl	40	404	400	-0.99

reveal the highest ion-exchange capacity for antimony(v) tungstate. The material was highly selective for some toxic transition metal ions. Other prepared tungstates showed selectivity for some other metal ions, mainly alkali metal

ions. Owing to the greater selectivity behavior of the exchanger for some toxic transition metal ions, it may be utilized for the removal and recovery of these ions from dilute water samples. The exchanger is useful in environmental

Table 4. A comparative study of ion-exchangers prepared so for with antimony(v) tungstate

Sl. no.	Material	Type of exchanger	Composition	Empirical formula	Ion-exchange capacity meq/g	Selectivity
1.	Zirconium tungstate	Amorphous	Zr/W = 1.0-0.44	-	-	Cs ^I , Rb ^I , K ^I , Na ^I , Li ^I
2.	Tin(IV) tungstate	Semi-transparent	Sn/W = 0.33	-	0.58	Ba ^{II} , Sr ^{II} , Pb ^{II} , Cu ^{II}
3.	Titanium tungstate	Amorphous	-	-	0.4-0.76	Cs ^I , Mg ^{II} , Ca ^{II}
4.	Thorium tungstate	Amorphous	Th/W = 2.0	Th(OH) ₂ (HWO ₄) ₂ .nH ₂ O	0.46	Cs ^I , K ^I , Na ^I
5.	Cerium tungstate	Amorphous	Ce ⁴⁺ /WO ₄ ²⁻ = 0.49	-	-	Tl ^I , Hg ^{II}
6.	Iron(III) tungstate	Amorphous	Fe/W = 1.0	-	0.84	Ce ^{IV}
7.	Chromium tungstate	Amorphous	W/Cr = 1.92	Cr ₂ O ₃ (H ₂ WO ₄) ₄ .11H ₂ O	0.02	Th ^{IV} , Hf ^{IV}
8.	Bismuth tungstate	Amorphous	Bi/W = 0.5	-	0.74	Pb ^{II}
9.	Antimony(v) tungstate	Amorphous	Sb/W = 2.25	[(Sb ₂ O ₅)(H ₂ WO ₄) _{2.5}].7.5H ₂ O	1.0	Hg ^{II} , Cr ^{VI} , Ru ^{VIII} , Pt ^{IV} , Al ^{III} , Pb ^{II}

analysis and pollution control.

The method is quite simple and highly selective for some metal ions. The ion-exchange column can be used repeatedly after its regeneration with $1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HNO}_3$.

Recoveries of Cr^{VI} , Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} from 1000 ml water samples (pH ~ 2) were studied. The samples were spiked with 10 and 50 mg of Cr^{VI} , 10, 50 and 100 mg of Hg^{II} and 10 and 50 mg of Pb^{II} , respectively, and analyzed by standard procedure (average of five determinations). The results reveal quantitative recoveries.

Experimental

Antimony(v) chloride (B.D.H.) and sodium tungstate (C.D.H.) were used. All other reagents were of A.R. grade and used as such.

Synthesis of exchanger : Antimony(v) tungstate was prepared by mixing decimolar solutions of antimony(v) chloride and sodium tungstate under various conditions. The ion exchange capacity of the various samples of antimony(v) tungstate was determined for Na^+ ions by column method.

The chemical composition of various samples of antimony(v) tungstate (AT_1) was reported. The powdered exchanger (AT_1 ; 0.50 g) was dissolved in hot $10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NaOH}$ (20 ml) adding tartaric acid (2g) and the alkaline solution was acidified³. Antimony was precipitated as sulfide and was determined with potassium iodide⁴; tungsten was determined by α -benzoin oxime method⁵. The molar composition was found to be 2 : 2.5 for Sb : W.

Distribution studies : K_d values of 16 transition metal

ions in DMW, HCl, HCl + 10% DMSO (1 : 10) and NH_4Cl systems were determined by batch process⁶. Pt^{IV} with potassium iodide, Ru^{VIII} with thiourea and Cr^{VI} with diphenylcarbazine were determined spectrophotometrically⁷ and other metal ions were determined using EDTA titration.

On the basis of differences in K_d values, some quantitative separations of analytically important metal ions were performed on the small column of antimony(v) tungstate. The eluted metal ions were determined by EDTA titration or by spectrophotometric method.

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